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SEVEN PRINCIPLES OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

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Abstract: This article describes the main concepts in the implementation of the 7 (principle) principles of Quality Management Systems in the standard.

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The ISO 9000 group of international standards defines the basic structure of Quality Management Systems (QMS) for the achievement of the organization's objectives, which clearly shows the basic concepts, principles and resources related to quality. These apply to all organizations, regardless of their size, complexity or business model. Its purpose is that organizations improve their sense of responsibility and commitment in meeting the needs of their customers and stakeholders, as well as in achieving their involvement in the provision of products and services.

In the international standard ISO 9000, important concepts in the implementation of the 7 (principles) of quality management systems are covered in paragraph 2.2. These principles are not requirements on their own, but they form basic requirements and are established in the requirements of the international standard ISO 9001.

7 principles of quality management systems

Principle 1: Involvement of the consumer

CONTENT: The main focus of quality management is to ensure the requirements of consumers and fulfill their wishes (ISO 9000:2015, 2.3.1).

AGREEMENT: High success is achieved when an organization must gain and maintain the trust of consumers and other stakeholders.

Aspects related to any consumer open the door of great opportunities for him. Understanding the needs of customers and other stakeholders today and in the future will lead the organization to sustainable success..

The main advantage:

- return of value for consumers;
- the return of consumer satisfaction;
- return of consumer loyalty;
- satisfaction of the volume of repeat orders;

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- increasing the reputation of the organization;
- expanding the geography of buyers;
- increase market share and profit.

Opportunity measures:

- identify direct and indirect consumers to whom the organization creates value;
- determine the current and future needs of consumers;
- connecting the organization's goals with the consumer's needs and expectations;
- communicating the needs and expectations of the consumer to all employees of the organization;
- to determine the planning, design, production, delivery and subsequent service of products and services in order to satisfy the needs and expectations of the consumer;
- monitoring and measuring whether the consumer is satisfied, whether the appropriate actions have been performed;
- identify and perform actions related to the needs and desires of interested parties, which affect consumer satisfaction;
- actively manage relationships with customers to achieve solid results.

Principle 2: Leadership

CONTENT: The organization should involve employees in achieving the goals set in the framework of quality, leaders at all levels, ensure a single goal and be leaders in creating an improvement environment (ISO 9000:2015, 2.3.2).

APPROPRIATENESS: Focus on ensuring and developing a single purpose, and in engaging employees, the organization is aligned with its strategy, policies, processes and has the resources to achieve the goals.

Leadership is not an administrative activity, but the leader has a single goal, and in achieving it, he should lead and give his employees!

One of the most important and urgent tasks is to educate a leader, but not everyone can be a leader at once, he also needs a team and an environment that will allow him to fully demonstrate his leadership potential.

The main advantage:

- return of effectiveness and efficiency in the achievement of the organization's quality goals;
- best coordination of organizational processes;
- improvement of awareness between levels and tasks of the organization;

- the nature of development and improvement of the organization, as well as increasing the level of its employees to achieve the necessary results. **Opportunity**

measures:

- conveying the organization's mission, vision, strategy, policy, immediate goals and processes to all employees;

- creation and preservation of common values, honesty and culture (ethics) principles at all levels of the organization;

- creation of an environment of trust and consensus;

- all employees are encouraged according to their contribution in achieving quality results;

- ensuring that leaders of all levels are positive role models for employees of the organization;

- give necessary resources, training and rights to employees to fulfill their responsibilities;

- Timely recognition and encouragement of employees' contributions.

Principle 3: Involvement of employees

CONTENT: Competence, accountability and empowerment of employees at all levels of the organization leads to added value and increased creativity (ISO 9000:2015, 2.3.3).

ADVANTAGE: Respecting the individuality of employees at all levels is essential for effective and efficient management of the organization.

In order to achieve the goals of the organization, they are the methods of recognition, empowerment, increasing the skills and knowledge of the employee.

The wide and productive use of people's abilities in cooperation and participation will bring benefits to the organization. **It is very important to fulfill their wishes!**

"No one can make you rich except the people who work for you" SONI company Akio Morita.

The main advantage:

- better understanding of the employee's goals of the organization in terms of quality and the return of incentives when they are achieved;

- more involvement of employees to improve their activities;

- expansion of opportunities for personal development, initiative and creativity;

- increase employee satisfaction;

- increase of trust and cooperation in the organization;
- increasing attention to corporate culture and common values in the organization.

Opportunity measures:

- formation of the understanding of the importance of their contribution for relations with employees;
- to provide an opportunity for cooperation throughout the organization;
- exchange of experience and knowledge, as well as an opportunity for open discussion;
- giving people the right to open problems at work and to take the initiative without fear;
- awarding and recognizing people according to their contribution, enriching their experience and development;
- provision of an opportunity to self-assess one's duties in terms of achieving personal goals;
- conducting surveys to assess people's satisfaction, reporting the results and taking appropriate measures.

Principle 4: Process approach

CONTENT: When activities are based on a systematic approach and management of interrelated processes and tasks, the achievement of appropriate and expected results will be more effective and efficient.

(ISO 9000:2015, 2.3.4).

ADVANTAGE: Quality management systems are made up of interrelated processes, the formation of systems on the basis of results leads to understanding, coordination of the organization's tasks and its work. The transformation of input into output is called a process approach.

When the ORGANIZATION's activities and available resources are viewed as a process, the above results will be effective!

The main advantage:

- focusing on the main processes and increasing the overall opportunity for improvement;
- coordination of the developed system with the processes, giving appropriate and expected results;

- coordination of tasks, effective use of resources and reduction of obstacles between tasks due to the result management of processes (function);
- the organization convinces interested parties of its reliable, effective and efficient capabilities.

Opportunity measures:

- determination of system and process goals to achieve the necessary results;
- establishment of rights, responsibility and reporting for process management;
- to determine the limit on resources before the implementation of measures and to understand the possibility of organization;
- finding process dependencies and analyzing the impact of any process changes on the entire system;
- management of processes and their interdependence in order for the organization to effectively and efficiently achieve its quality goals;
- ensuring ease of obtaining information for the necessary management and improvement of processes, as well as assessment, monitoring and analysis of the entire system function;
- managing risks that affect the results of the entire quality management system and processes.

Principle 5: continuous improvement

CONTENT: Focusing on continuous improvement will always bring success to the organization (ISO 9000:2015, 2.3.5).

ADVANTAGES: Creating new opportunities in an environment of internal and external change is vital for an organization to improve with a view to maintaining the current level of functioning.

The set goals are achieved by continuously improving processes, products, and systems based on benchmarking, evaluation, and analysis.

Continuous improvement (Sontinual improvement) is the upward growth with small, reliable changes!

Take repeated measures to improve performance.

The main advantage:

- improvement of process tasks, increase of organizational capacity and customer satisfaction;

- increasing attention to the search and identification of the root cause with corrective and preventive measures;
- improvement of identification and elimination of internal and external risks and opportunities;
- Continuous development and continuous improvement report on further expansion of opportunities;
- further expansion of the application of accumulated experiences for improvement;
- directing improvement to modern innovations.

Opportunity measures:

- striving for the goals set for improving the organization at all levels;
- to teach employees of all levels how to use the main instruments and methods for the implementation of improvement goals and to develop their skills;
- to successfully initiate and complete improvement projects;
- spread and develop processes for implementation of improvement projects throughout the organization;
- achievement, monitoring, audit planning and analysis of improvement projects and their results;
- reporting on improvements in process/product and service changes or creation of new ones;
- recognize and reward improvements in a timely manner.

Principle 6. Making decisions based on evidence

CONTENT: By evaluating results and data and making decisions based on analysis, the probability of achieving the objectives is very high (ISO 9000:2015, 2.3.6).

ADVANTAGE: The decision-making process is complex and always involves unknown uncertainty. Decision-making is sometimes based on the type of inputs and sources, and the notions of what they are equal to. The effects and causes of the processes involved in decision-making, as well as the possible consequences must be understood.

Analyzing information, results and evidence leads to accurate and reliable decision making.

The main advantage:

- improving processes by making decisions;
- improving the assessment of tasks and processes of achieving the goal;
- improvement of effectiveness and efficiency;
- expansion of opportunities for changing decisions and opinions, checking and learning;

- expanding the opportunity to demonstrate the effectiveness of previously adopted decisions.

Opportunity measures:

- organization tasks to set important indicators for presenting results, perform monitoring and measurements;

- to provide convenient delivery of all necessary information to employees;

- to ensure the accuracy, reliability and security of this information;

- evaluation and analysis of results and data using appropriate methods;

- to ensure the guarantee of the appropriate level of competence of the employees, which is necessary for the evaluation and analysis of the results;

- make and implement decisions based on evidence, superior experience and judgment.

Principle 7 Relationship Management

CONTENT: An organization must manage interactions with stakeholders (eg suppliers) to ensure sustainable success (ISO 9000:2015, 2.3.7).

CONVENIENCE: Stakeholder attitudes affect organizational performance. An organization is more likely to achieve sustainable success when it can effectively manage its activities with stakeholders.

Especially supplier and partner relationship management (m: price, contract, knowledge, resource, improvement, profit, etc.) is very important.

The main advantage:

- the organization and interested parties improve the results of activities related to each party, taking into account opportunities and limits;

- stakeholders' understanding of common capabilities and goals;

- expand value creation for stakeholders through resource sharing and skill enhancement, as well as quality risk management;

- effective management of the supply chain, which ensures a stable flow of products and service processes.

Opportunity measures:

- to identify interested parties (such as suppliers, partners, consumers, shareholders, investors, employees and the whole society) and the related aspect of the organization with them;
- identification of interrelationships with interested parties that need to be managed;
- orientation to interdependence, taking into account the equality of near and far interests;
- gathering and providing relevant information, knowledge and resources to interested parties;
- providing feedback with interested parties and evaluating the work results for how to apply these, to improve the initiative;
- developing and improving the supply chain together with the consumer, organization, supplier, partner and other interested parties;
- improving the presenter and timely recognition and encouragement of his successes.

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